

A convolutional neural network as a proxy for the XRF approximation of the chemical composition of archaeological artefacts in the presence of inter-microscope variability

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Abstract. The paper puts forward a convolutional neural network model for multi-output regression, which is trained on images from two distinct microscope types to estimate the concentration of a pair of chemical elements from the surface of archaeological metal objects. The target is to simulate the approximation behaviour of the more complex XRF technology, which is used as ground truth in training the model. Experiments investigate the adequacy of learning on either type of data and then using the models to test images coming from each microscope in turn and in combination. Under these terms of performance and flexibility, the technology can be successfully used in the front line of ancient object restoration across laboratories irrespective of the equipment available.

Keywords: convolutional neural networks, multi-output regression, chemical estimation, XRF, inter-microscope variability, archaeology

1 Introduction

Historical artefacts undergo complex restoration and conservation procedures in their journey from excavation to museum display. But, in order to decide the best methods, a thorough assessment of the objects must be conducted first [8]. Various partially invasive methods are performed for the elemental analysis regarding alloy composition, proteic nature, acidity, solubility, ink type, color, and measurements of physical, chemical, mechanical and biological degradation. In opposition to these, several non-invasive, non-destructive qualitative and quantitative approaches can be used to investigate the material structure of objects. The surface of the artefact can be examined through optical analysis (optical

and electron microscopes, endoscopes) and photo-fixing (cameras, lighting or irradiation with UV or IR). In this way, the forms of corrosion layers, textures, iridescence, blistering, erosion, deposition, finishing, sanding, polishing, inlaying, watermarks can be determined. On the other hand, direct assessment techniques have been employed in recent years, namely reflectography, radiography, atomic spectrometry - X-ray fluorescence (XRF), and trace analysis.

XRF spectrometry is a method of non-destructive and non-invasive instrumental analysis [10], also suitable for portable devices, that can provide coherent and reliable estimations about the analyzed heritage asset. The primary X-rays are emitted from an X-ray tube and the characteristic X-rays released by the analyzed object, under the impact of the electron beam, come from a maximum depth of $5\mu\text{m}$ and are used for elementary chemical analysis at the surface. The measurements can only be made for chemical elements from Be to U. The light elements cannot be analyzed, because the X-rays emitted by them are absorbed by the air. The extensive use of the machine is limited however by its cost, the required training, and a small possibility of radioactivity.

On the other hand, microscopes of distinct types with different magnification and resolution levels are largely available in all museum laboratories. Therefore, provided sufficient microscopic samples of object surfaces, a convolutional neural network (CNN) could learn to approximate the chemical concentrations of the main elements in the composition of the item to resemble the XRF estimation.

The effectiveness of the CNN approach may however assume a repeated, regular way of microscopic data collection in various restoration labs and museums. Nevertheless, this desirable asset is hindered by variation in imaging quality and consistency when taken by different microscopes. Therefore, the aim of the current paper is to train a CNN architecture on images taken by one stereo microscope and one electron device, of distinct performances, using the XRF approximation as ground truth for learning. Several experimental settings are envisaged in order to evaluate the difference between training separately or on the combination of the two microscopic image types for recognizing test examples produced by each machine.

The surface of an object shows the presence of several chemical elements, but the expert restorer solely considers the main one (or two) components, i.e. those with a concentration above 25%. The study therefore considers the analysis of two elements, namely copper (Cu) and iron (Fe), that are present in large concentrations and in a sufficient number of artefacts. A multiple output regression problem is formulated and the CNN model is applied for solving the task.

The paper is structured in the following manner. Section 2 introduces the data set and the two types of microscopic images on the selected pair of chemical elements (Cu, Fe). The appointed CNN methodology for their analysis is presented in Section 4, while the state of the art related to recent computational intelligence support for the chemical investigation of the XRF in archaeology is depicted in Section 3. The experiments on the various configurations for the training set and the results on every type of microscopic image per studied element are discussed in Section 5. Section 6 establishes the final conclusions.

2 Materials

The data are available from the Oltenia Museum - the History and Archaeology Section, Craiova, Romania. The set encompasses artefacts brought for restoration at the museum laboratory during the months January - April 2021.

Every item was examined under the microscope and photographed in the areas adjacent to the XRF point of analysis. Both a stereo microscope and an electron microscope were used. The former is an Olympus SZX-7 optical stereo microscope equipped with a Quick Photo Micro 2.2 digital camera. The latter is a portable LCD digital microscope, model G600. The difference between the two is that, while the electron one is a common, simple device, the stereo optical system of SZX-7 offers a superior quality of the image, especially when used together with the digital camera. The stereoscopic system uses two independent and parallel optical channels, offering color high fidelity, noise reduction, and increased modularity for imaging. A general purpose electron microscope is more accessible in conservation labs everywhere. In this sense, from the practical perspective, it is important to know if the CNN approach is independent of the machine that takes the samples. Hence, we considered 65 objects which were photographed by the stereo microscope and produced 482 images, and 21 artefacts that were given to the electron device and led to 124 images. The chemical investigation of the objects was done by means of a portable Bruker Titan S1 XRF spectrometer, together with the specific software Artax. Each microscopic sample thus has attached the concentration values approximated by the XRF as ground truth.

Figure 1 shows examples of images derived from both types of microscopes. The two elements considered in the analysis, i.e. Fe and Cu, were chosen because most artefacts are built upon the metallurgy principles of strength and performance of either the Bronze or Iron Ages. Also, based on the same production concepts, their role is different in the composition of an ancient object: while Fe is strongly predominant, Cu is generally present as part of an alloy. The XRF estimation of the quantity of the two elements accompanies each image.

3 State of the art

Deep learning support for microscopy image analysis is performed largely, but with preponderance within the medical domain [3,7,9,18], while architectures for several applications in materials science in general have also been considered [12,13,15]. On the other hand, the XRF output in archaeology has been investigated only by a small number of statistical and artificial intelligence methods. Besides the numerical estimation of the elemental concentrations in the object, the XRF also gives a plot of energy versus photon counts, called a spectrum [4]. In the current literature, the entries on machine learning in tandem with XRF address the sampling or analysis of the XRF spectra. A Monte Carlo algorithm is constructed in [1] to simulate the XRF spectra in application to metal artefacts. The paper [11] also employs the Monte Carlo technique to simulate the

Fig. 1. Samples of images taken from artefacts both from stereo and electron microscopy. The chemical concentrations of Fe and Cu estimated by the XRF are outlined above each image, with the predominant metal highlighted in bold.

XRF spectra; a neural network for multi-output regression subsequently uses the resulting spectra to approximate the chemical concentration of five metals. In the different field of geology, the study [4] puts forward an analysis-by-synthesis auto-encoder that employs XRF spectral data to estimate the composition of several elements from rocks with geochemical assay as the ground truth. The inverse problem of taking the elemental concentrations given by the XRF and using them as predictors for the type of a (ceramic) object is tackled in [2] by means of k -nearest neighbors, decision trees, and learning vector quantization.

In opposition, the current paper attempts to offer a XRF-independent and device-independent tool for approximating the chemical concentrations of the main elements in an archaeological artefact. A CNN is trained on images from two microscopes to output an approximation of the concentrations of Cu and Fe, and the result is compared to the XRF estimate. A primary attempt to appraise the quantity of two metals separately from a data set of stereo microscopy images only has been proposed in [19] and acknowledged the potential of combining microscopy, XRF, and deep learning.

4 Method

The task of concentration estimation is formulated as a multiple output regression problem. Given a set of images $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m\}$, the assignment is to predict associated targets $y_i^j \in \mathbb{R}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, $j \in \{1, 2\}$. Since the deep network must produce a multi-output result, after the sequence of the convolutional layers, and once the last volume is flattened, the architecture branches into separate dense layers for each desired output. A well known application of such a multi-output CNN is the simultaneous age and gender prediction [14].

In the current task, the targets y_i^1 and y_i^2 correspond to the numerical assessments of the percent of Fe and Cu respectively, which result from the analysis

of the i -th microscopic image. In previous work [19], we treated each output as a separate task for the CNN. However, when presented with a new item, it is clearly more efficient to run just one model that is able to determine the approximations of all possibly constituent elements, than testing it on every one model tailored for one particular metal. Moreover, this multi-output approach resembles more the behaviour of the XRF technology in estimating the chemical composition of an artefact.

The CNN takes in the images and the related pair of concentration estimations from the XRF. The practical question that arises at this point is whether the model will be further able to rightly estimate the concentrations, given that test images are potentially produced by a different microscope. This aspect will be debated in the experimental Section 5.

Given the limited amount of actual microscopic samples, especially when not combining the images from both microscopes for training, a pre-trained model is used to prevent overfitting, defining mean squared error (MSE) as loss function.

Apart from the regression specific metrics of MSE and mean/median absolute errors (MAE/MedAE), the performance of the model will also be measured through one that allows for a margin of error, called accuracy@ t and first introduced in the study [16] for age prediction. An exact value for the elemental concentration is not necessary, as the ground truth itself is an estimation given by the point on which the XRF is applied, where deposits of corrosion might have hindered its approximation [10]. As such, given a margin of error of $\pm t$, the CNN prediction for a sample $x_i \in X$ is deemed correct for output j in comparison to the XRF ground truth \hat{y}_i^j if $|y_i^j - \hat{y}_i^j| < t$. This metric was also applied in the early study [19] and the results were deemed by the experts to be informative for the restoration procedures.

5 Experiments

Different training sets are taken to evaluate the dependence of the results on the microscopic type of input images that are considered. The setup of the experiments is next described and is followed by the results and a discussion about their interpretation.

5.1 Experimental setup

There are three settings established for training the CNN models. In one of them the Resnet34 and Densenet201 architectures are trained only on samples from stereo microscope, in the second one the training is based only on images from the electron microscope, and in the last one the models are built on the slides coming from both microscopes. In all scenarios, the results from the test set are provided too for all three cases, i.e. only for images from stereo-microscope, only from the electron one, and combined.

Each object has between 1 and 17 microscopical images, depending on its size. The images that appear in the test set belong to objects different than those that

have microscopical pictures in the training/validation sets. The distribution of the items between training and test sets is shown in Table 1, both at the image and at the object levels.

Table 1. Number of images and objects for the k -fold cross-validation and for test.

Microscope	Image level		Object level	
	Training/validation	Test	Training/validation	Test
Stereo	413	69	57	8
Electron	97	27	17	4

Figure 2 illustrates the amount of Fe and Cu in microscopical images from each type of device, as they appear both in the training/validation and test sets.

Fig. 2. Sample frequency for images from simple and stereo microscopes for Fe (top row) and Cu (bottom row) and for training/validation items (left plots) and test ones (right plots).

The training/validation set is split using k -fold cross-validation with $k = 5$. For each split, the models learn from the training part and are validated on the remaining $1/5$ set. The best model obtained in validation for each of the 5 splits is also applied on the test set. Consequently, the reported output for the validation set, as well as the one for the test set, is computed by averaging the results obtained over the 5 cross-validation rounds. The same data set splits are used for Fe and Cu, as well as for each architecture in turn.

Similar settings are considered for both architectures. All images are resized to 224×224 pixels. An additional final layer is appended to each of the 2 architectures with the aim of maintaining the outputs of the models inside the interval $[0, 100]$. This is done by replacing negative values with 0 and numbers larger than 100 with 100. The 1cycle policy follows the procedure in [17] and uses the implementation in [6]. It is used for the training process in 2 steps. Within the first training session, the model uses a discriminative learning rate for 50 epochs. The learning rate starts from a low value of $1e-05$ for the first layers, continues up to $1e-04$ for the middle layers, and reaches $1e-01$ in the final layers. The model with the lowest validation MSE obtained from each of the cross-validation rounds and each architecture is then reloaded, has all its layers unfrozen and is trained for an additional 10 epochs with a learning rate tuned automatically [6].

For the first training session, we used an additional early stopping criterion of 30 epochs without improvement, but this maneuver appeared in just 13.33% of the cases and even here the number of epochs was only reduced in average by 9 epochs, i.e. taking 37 epochs in the shortest run and 45 in the longest one.

The parameter for the number of epochs from the initial session of training was tuned during pre-experimental setup from 10 up to 100 in steps of 10 using only the Resnet34 architecture. The results were usable in all combinations, but they were relatively stabilized from 50 epochs and up. Still, even for lower number of epochs, the MSE were still viable (although slightly higher), which suggests that the number of epochs could be reduced in the case training times happen to be an issue. Hence, a value of 50 epochs is considered for this important parameter. Finally, a batch size of 32 is considered.

Data augmentation is performed due to the relatively small data set. The options used in this sense are the following: random flip (horizontal and vertical flips together with rotations by 90 degrees are allowed with a probability of 0.5), rotation (a random rotation between -180 and 180 degrees is applied with probability 0.5), symmetric warp (random and allowed between -0.3 and 0.3 with the same probability 0.5), random resize and crop (with the same probability, resizes and crops are applied to images using a zoom of 2; the method, initially proposed in [5], uses points that determine the center of the resulting image and switches from one to another).

The output results are computed as MSE, MAE, and MedAE, for the samples in the test set. The reported results are calculated as average from the outputs of the models obtained from the 5-fold cross-validation as applied on the test samples for each type of image (as concerns the microscope that produced it) in turn. Additionally, we also compute a classification accuracy in which a threshold t is set to allow a window of error such that if the XRF estimated value for a metal in an image is \hat{y}_i^j , the predicted value is considered to be correct if it lies within the range $[\hat{y}_i^j - t, \hat{y}_i^j + t]$.

5.2 Results and discussion

Table 2 illustrates the MSE, MAE, and MedAE average results from the outcomes on the test set from the 5-fold cross-validation models. Every training set (stereo, electron, and combined) is considered separately and, for each category, the models are applied on the test set that contain images from the stereo microscope, from the electron device, and from the combination of both, showing the results in different rows. The first column, *Test all*, refers to the results on all test samples, both those that originate from the electron and the stereo microscope, and also aggregates the results from Fe and Cu. The next column, *Stereo all*, contains only stereo images, and refers to the results from both metals, whereas the column *Electron all* refers to the corresponding result coming from electron images from the test set. Finally, the columns *Fe all*, *Cu all* refers to the stereo and electron samples that correspond only to the Fe or Cu measurements, respectively. The remaining columns refer to the indicated subgroups for combinations of a particular metal and a particular device.

Table 2. Average MSE, MAE, and MedAE results for both architectures and for each training/validation type in turn.

Trained on	Test all	Stereo all	Electron all	Fe all	Cu all	Fe stereo	Cu stereo	Fe electron	Cu electron
ResNet-34 MSE									
Combined	186.3	117.6	361.7	158.6	213.9	61.6	173.7	406.7	316.8
Stereo	203.6	122.8	410	119.3	287.9	51.5	194.2	292.6	527.4
Electron	1119.2	1399.6	402.6	1647.3	591.1	2120.4	678.9	438.4	366.8
ResNet-34 MAE									
Combined	9	7.2	13.8	8.2	9.9	5.5	8.9	15.1	12.5
Stereo	9.4	6.8	16	7.1	11.6	4.4	9.2	14.2	17.9
Electron	25.6	29.6	15.2	31.3	19.8	37.4	21.8	15.8	14.7
ResNet-34 MedAE									
Combined	4.4	3.9	6.8	4.6	4.2	4.3	3.7	6.8	6.7
Stereo	4.78	3.1	13.1	4.4	6.2	3.1	2.9	11.7	14.5
Electron	21	22.3	11.4	26.8	19	37	21	11.3	11.5
DenseNet-201 MSE									
Combined	158.3	112.5	275.1	131.2	185.3	36.3	188.8	373.7	176.4
Stereo	241.7	131.9	522.2	135.8	347.5	25.3	238.5	418.2	626.2
Electron	1149.3	1446	391.1	1504.3	794.2	1937.1	954.9	398.4	383.8
DenseNet-201 MAE									
Combined	8.2	6.7	12.2	7.5	9	4.7	8.6	14.4	10
Stereo	9.7	6.5	17.9	7.1	12.2	3.5	9.4	16.4	19.5
Electron	26.8	31.1	15.8	30.6	23	36.9	25.4	14.7	16.9
DenseNet-201 MedAE									
Combined	4.2	3.6	7.5	4.2	4.1	3.9	2.7	9	7.1
Stereo	4.1	2.8	16	3.6	5.8	2.9	2.4	15.9	16.2
Electron	20.8	28.7	14.1	23.5	18.2	36.7	21.6	13.2	15.9

As concerns the running times, the entire procedure of training in two steps and tuning for finding the appropriate learning rate, as well as applying the model on the test set, takes 22 minutes for the combined data for ResNet-34 and 30 minutes for DenseNet-201. When using only the stereo data, the running times decrease to 15 minutes for the former architecture and 19 for the latter. For the electron data, the times reduce further to 9.7 minutes and 11.5, respectively. The application of the models on the test set takes around 4 seconds for either architecture, which means that for testing one image it takes 0.04 seconds. All runs and time measurements are made using Google Colab and a Tesla T4 GPU. Testing an image using CPU also in Google Colab takes significantly more, but the running time remains under a second, i.e. 0.31 seconds.

We next assess the proposed methodology as a classification task, according to the $\text{accuracy}@t$ index [16], i.e. when an image is considered to be correctly classified for a metal if the estimation error is less than a threshold t . In our experiments, the threshold that defines the width of the allowed error interval is varied from 1 to 30, and the results are shown in Figure 3, illustrating the classification accuracy in all discussed scenarios.

By evaluating separately the two types of data stemming from the respective microscopes, it can be seen that the limited number of samples from the electron one is well reflected by the results. When the training and validation is made on the stereo microscope, the test on the data of the same type leads MSE values of 122.8 and 131.9 for ResNet-34 and DenseNet-201, respectively. Conversely, when the training and testing is made on the data from the electron microscope, the corresponding results are of 402.6 and 391.1, respectively. The decrease in quality for the data coming from the electron microscope is additionally caused by the fact that Fe has 11 samples in the test set that have a percentage of 56%, while the training data for this metal contains either artefacts that are very low on Fe or pieces with high quantities. Moreover, such lack of samples with an intermediate percentage for Fe occurs also for the stereo one.

The hardest task lies in the recognition of the percentage of Fe in examples coming from the stereo microscope when the training is made only on samples from the electron microscope. There is only a small amount of samples with high percentages of electron Fe in the training, while the number of stereo test images with similarly high percentage is large. At the opposite end, the Cu is better spread for percentages between 25% and 90% on both the electron training and stereo test sets, hence the significantly better results in this scenario.

The results do not show a clear general winner between the two tested architectures, ResNet-34 and DenseNet-201. When learning from the data set with combined images, the results appear to have a slight advantage for DenseNet-201, both in Table 2 and in the Figure 3. On the other hand, in the case when the training is made only on the data from the electron microscope, the ResNet-34 has better results in general than DenseNet-201. However, the results are not significantly better for one versus another, hence the running time might prove decisive in preferring ResNet34 for the task.

Fig. 3. Classification accuracy as obtained by Densenet201 and Resnet34 for Fe (left column) and Cu (right column), for varied approximation thresholds of the accuracy@ t index, when training is performed on combined data (first row), stereo microscope data (middle), and electron microscope samples (bottom).

As a general conclusion on the experimental findings, the ideal case would be if all labs had stereo microscopes available for a high definition output of the object surface. In this situation, with the training performed also only on stereo, the estimation error on new examples would be very low. But, since in the real-world scenario, restoration facilities rather have general purpose devices, having a training made on many samples stemming from various types of microscopes will lead to a good test approximation whatever the device.

6 Conclusions

The current paper explores the possibility of employing a CNN that analyzes microscopy images of archaeological artefacts to simulate the XRF approximation of the chemical elemental concentration present on the surface. A dual output regression is formulated for Fe and Cu and the use of different types of microscopes (stereo and electron) to produce the training images is investigated.

As expected, the results from the models trained on samples originating from the electron microscope are generally poor, demonstrating thus the need to acquire more data of this type, in order to balance the data set. The combined approach (results from the first row in each section from Table 2 and the plots from the first row in Figure 1) encourage us to believe that the models will be able to generalize well and estimate the quantity of the metals well, even if the images come from different types of microscopes.

Future work will include the consideration of a higher number of samples produced by the electron microscope. It is also intended to use other elements present in archaeological assets, such as silver, tin, lead or silicon, with a corresponding increase in the number of examined artefacts to include them.

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